

CHROMATOMASS- SPECTROMETRIC STUDY OF DRY EXTRACTS OF SEDUM L. OBTAINED BY DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

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One of the promising sources of herbal medicines are medicinal plants containing a complex of biologically active substances. Due to their wide distribution in plants and great structural diversity, these drugs can be used in the treatment of diseases of various etiologies. In order to effectively develop new agents with a maximum concentration of biologically active substances for the treatment of a specific disease, it is necessary to select conditions for extraction [1,2].

The purpose of the study is to obtain a dry extract using water, 70% ethyl alcohol, 80% ethyl alcohol as extractants and determine by mass-spectroscopic method biologically active substances dissolved in methanol.

Materials and methods. Chromatography-mass spectrometry and analyzes were carried out on a chromatograph M. "Agilent technologies 7890b, GS System, mass selective detector "5977a MDS" - Masshunter drugs_scanag-3666.

The discussion of the results. In the mass spectrum of the dry extract obtained using water as an extractant, biologically active substances such as ethyl cholate (cholic acid ethyl ester), ethyl glycoside, borredin, which is a bile acid derivative with an antimicrobial effect, astaxanthin, were found carotenoid exhibiting antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects

In the mass spectrum of the dry extract obtained using 70% ethyl alcohol as an extractant, biologically active substances such as ethyl glycoside, luxantine, a biologically active substance were found that promotes the proper functioning of the eyes and improves vision, betulin - has hepatoprotective, choleric, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antiviral, immunomodulatory, hypolipidemic, gastroprotective effects; sitosterol is used to reduce high cholesterol levels.

80% ethyl alcohol as an extractant, such biologically active substances as ethyl glycoside, ethyl palmitate used as a hair and skin care product, phytol (florazol , phytosol) acyclic hydrogenated were found diterpene alcohol, which is used as a precursor for the production of synthetic forms of vitamin E and vitamin K1, β -tocopherol, γ -tocopherol, methyl lignocerate , β - sitosterol , various vitamin E derivatives.

Conclusions Sedum, which has a unique chemical composition, exhibits a wide range of pharmacological effects. To effectively develop new medicines from sedum with a maximum concentration of biologically active substances for the treatment of a specific disease, it is necessary to select a rational extractant and optimal extraction conditions.

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